

Research on School Bus Economical Operation in Chinese Rural Compulsory Education—School Buses Operation in our Supporting Education as case

Author's Details:

(1) **Jikun Liu** - Lake Forest Academy, IL, United States- (2) **Yanhan Li** - Worcester Academy, MA, United States

Abstract: *After approximately 100 years of development, the school bus operation of United States has formed a well-functioning system, which regulates the standard of school bus production and management as well as augments into a professional service industry. This article, after learning the advanced operational methodology of the United States, incorporating the experience that we acquired during the Summer vocation and Winter breaks for the last two years, will discuss the economical operation of Chinese school buses in rural areas and optimistically would work as reference for the prospective formulation of a systematic, secure, and professional rural school bus service.*

Key Words: *Economical Operation/School Bus/Compulsory Education/Rural Area in China*

Dated Back to 1939, the school bus methodology of the United States becomes the most well-consummated, systematic, safe, and professional one in the world with collaboration of society and government. As the one of China, after the initiation of Act “School Withdrawal and Mergence” in 2001, increasing need of rural school buses has forced the Government to enact “The Safety Technique Condition of Special Using School Bus for Primary Scholar” on July 1st, 2010 officially, yet the effect was proven very limited for that the present insufficiency was still significant. The major reason for such gap was the deficiency of funding on the apparatus as well as the management. Thereby, this article will focus on the efficient and economic running of school buses from two approaches of “expanding the resources” and “average the traffic flow and cut extraneousness” and optimistically would work as reference for the prospective formulation of a systematic, secure, and professional rural school bus service.

1. The Theoretical Cost of Manufacturing School Bus

Contemporarily, the most common way of school bus management is that central and local governments are responsible for sponsoring and that corporations, non-government organizations, schools, or students' parents are responsible for empirical administration and running of school buses.

The Chinese Ministry of Education stated that the shortage of investments was one of the major problems during the expansion on the scale of school bus services. If the government wants to guarantee the school bus service for elementary schools and compulsory education, 300,000,000,000 Chinese yuan (approximately \$46.2 billion) will be required to satisfy such need, while the annual fee of running and maintenance will be up to 150,000,000,000 Chinese yuan (approximately \$23.1 billion); as a conclusion, the governmental input will be beyond its affordability. However, using this calculation, assuming elementary students makes up one half of this population, in which rural elementary students only makes up one fifth of all elementary students, the required fund for only rural elementary students will lower to the one tenth of the original cost, which turns out to be about 30,000,000,000 Chinese yuan (\$4.6 billion).

Take a different approach. That the national educational funding takes up 4% of GDP is the basic level for the evaluation of education internationally. Many countries in the world have been holding up a comparatively high level of education fund. (Table 1) Early in 2001, the proportion of education fund of the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia and these countries with high average income reached 4.8%, while the ones of Columbia, Cuba, and those countries with comparatively low average income reached a level of 5.6%.

Table 1 the Ratio of Education Fund to GDP of Major Countries in the World (%)

Name	2011	2012	2013	Average
Developed Countries				

United States	5.2			5.2
United Kingdom	5.8			5.8
France	5.5	5.5		5.5
Canada	5.3			5.3
Germany	4.8			4.8
Japan	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.8
Korea		4.6		4.6
Australia	5.1	4.9		5
Denmark	8.5			8.5
Finland	6.5	7.2		6.85
Sweden	6.5			6.5
Switzerland	5	5		5
New Zealand	7.1	7.4		7.25
South Africa	6	6.4	6	6.13
Developing Countries				
China (excluding HK, Aomen, Taiwan)	3.93	4.16	4.15	4.08
East Timor	9.5			9.5
Malaysia	5.9			5.9
Vietnam		6.3		6.3
Brazil	6.1	6.3		6.2
Thailand	5.2	4.9		5.05
Afganistan	4.1	3.1	4.6	3.93
India	3.9	3.9		3.9

Source: Education Public Funds are composed with Public Regular Expenditure and Capital Expenditure, including governmental fund on educational institution (public and private), educational management, and the subsidies for individuals (students, families or others).

Data of countries other than China are from UNESCO (The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization); see more details on website: <http://data.worldbank.org.cn/indicator/SE.XPD.TOTL.GD.ZS>;

Chinese Data are from National Bureau of Statistics; main page: <http://www.tjcn.org/>.

Normally, Education Public Funds are composed of the expense on the construction of school dormitory and the assemblage of certain quantity of school buses. In 2015, the GDP of China has reached 67,670,800,000,000, a 6.9% increase compared to the one of precedent year. One of Chinese CPPCC members, economist Yining Li and his research team experimented with actual cases and conclude that when average (to each person) GDP has reached \$800 to \$1000, economy and education will both go on a virtuous circle only if Education Public Funds

reaches a percent of 4.07% to 4.25%. Accordingly, since the average GDP has already reached a level of \$8016, if the proportion of Education Public Funds can be raised to 4.25% rather than the current one, 4.08%, 24,500,000,000 Chinese yuan (approx. \$3.8 billion) will be available for further educational construction. Although it is barely possible for all 24,500,000,000 Chinese yuan (approx. \$3.8 billion) to be invested into the assemblage of school buses, due to the immense lack of school buses supply and investment, it is definitely worth an extension of the outlay on school bus production and management and magnification of the proportion of school bus investment in case all other educational funds are generally satisfied. Moreover, lowering the amount of immediate investment can ease the instantaneous pressure, while the addition of funds can be done gradually. Thus, in another word, if the proportion of Education Public Funds reaches the level of virtuous cycle, at least half of the initial purchase of school buses for Chinese rural area students will be out of concern.

2. Collective responsibility on the manufacture and management fee from Central government, local governments, and companies

In the United States, the service of free school bus ride for elementary and middle school students is considered one of the major parts of compulsory education; as long as one student lives one mile away from his school, he will be offered free school bus service, while gradually this school bus system develops into the most attentive and considerate school bus running administration scheme. Each level of government owns its distinct responsibility: federal government is majorly responsible for setting school bus security standards and optimizing relating legislation; state governments, according to local circumstances, specify legislation into details and are the major purchasers of school bus services; local governments are responsible for implement of these detailed legislation. School bus companies are the major providers for school bus services, responsible for all practical specific running services, while the transportation fee of the students from public schools are mainly dispensed by schools and school districts, financed by state government. The financial supports from federal and states governments, as well as from the social charities, are used to ensure the purchase, rental, management, renovation and repair, and etc. Besides, in order to intensify grasp on the quality and producing standard, the governments usually provides subsidies to the companies that produces school buses, while often less tax will be collected from the companies which provides large area school bus services. The mature and developed school bus running mode in the United States is highly worth reference; at the same time, if this mode and the temporary maturation of internet and social media technologies are integrated, there is to be many possible ways of school bus management for Chinese rural bus services.

2.1 Expand the governmental output; form school bus production chain

Statistically, school buses are the safest vehicle: in the United States, the rate of accident of each million kilometers for school buses is only 0.01, while the one of train is 0.04 and the one of plane is 0.06; for other vehicles, the rate is 0.096, proving school bus is actually 9 times safer, while this statistics has to originate from immense financial, technological, and public-service relating supports. Learning from this, the government should stretch up its funding, referring to the scheme of CAR (China Auto Rental) and accordingly adopt the way of uniform order of large quantity of school buses, enabling the government to save expanse and regulating the standards for applicable technologies and suitable indices on vehicles scales and functions. Using the United States as an example, due to the annual need of 46,000 new school buses, as well as the relating mending, parts production, a school bus production chain of \$15,000,000,000 each year is then formed. This type of business is already profitable for the companies involved, while the government will offer other privileges and subsidies during the process.

2.2 Optimize tax policies and nationally implement school bus tax reduction

School bus is an essential part of social public service system, and the construction of wide-spread low-cost/no-cost school bus services is a significant backup for the development of compulsory education; however, only a minuscule amount of local governments manage to include the school bus service into the planning expanse, indicating the stark lack of funds, as well as the conjectural low quantity and quality of existing school buses. The government, since being only able to provide limited amount of financial aids, should also

support this service by legislation such as free of tax on the business and manufacture of school buses, suitable amount of subsidies and trading privileges, canceling vehicle purchase tax, vehicle and ship usage fee, tolls fee of certain routes and bridges, etc.

2.3 Explore the path of “commonwealth-ization” and encourage the voluntary participation of corporations

“All purchased by the government” is actually considered a timeworn economical ideology now. Additionally, for now, buying all school buses by the government is quite a far reach goal for this short time interval; yet, it is worth trying to be collectively responsible for this charge by central government, local governments, and private enterprises, while schools can also solve the problem of school bus management fee themselves by the natural value increase of school buses, such as:

- a. Apply the technology of clean fuel, both protecting the environment and gaining the subsidies of the usage of clean fuel from the government, lowering the running cost;
- b. By scanning student ID cards upon going up the school bus, gather instantaneous information of students such as height, weight, etc. and sell data collected to third-party companies;
- c. Play videos or audios that help students learn, not only helping common students learn, but also training low-age hosts during the process; profitable engagement for many type of company in this process too;
- d. Play clips that especially stress the scientific events that are only available for rural students, such as petting little animals, growing edible fungi(which are super expansive currently), etc. Beside enhancing the extracurricular abilities, the companies also profits from such activities;
- e. Open up customized sale for elementary and middle school students; selectively play advertisements for suitable products.

2.4 Make further use of the market in the need of school bus production

In the United States, the routes are prescribed by education ministries in states government, and then the franchise are auctioned to the market, while the governments need only to adopt suitable policies to ensure the activeness and stability of the market; during the process, the new annual requirement of school buses are generally satisfied. Students’ transportation services that school bus contracted companies are comprehensively responsible for, including purchasing school buses, hiring drivers, keeping the quotidian running of the school buses and etc., can be more exposed to the market in order to improve efficiency. Government can provides more policy-wise privileges for these companies, while these companies can use its advantage of large scale and professionalization to make their service more efficient and safer, relieving the pressure and work on school and school district, curtailing cumbersome running management work. Up to now, the school buses being supervised by contracted companies are 39% of all school buses all over the United States, the famous ones being “First Student”, “National Express” and etc.

3. When using school service, make as much as possible efficiency share as possible and achieve averaging out the traffic flow

In a recent research conducted by Howley Craig, more than 85% of US rural area elementary students were reported to stay on school bus for more than 30 minutes, 25% of them for more than 60 minutes. Before the prescription of routes and implement of resulting scheme, it is necessary to research on the requirement of school bus for each district, such as the numbers of schools, scales of school, the average age of students, the quantity of students who takes school buses and etc; the routes and required amount of school buses can then be determined correspondingly. According to our interviews and research, the average service radius for Chinese rural school buses is 5 kilometers, which means that for each school bus, the average traveling distance per run is approximately 31.4 kilometers(circum.= $2*3.14*5\text{km}=31.4\text{km}$).

3.1 Crossing the schedule time for schools that are near to achieve the share of school buses

Drivers set off school buses between 7:00-9:30 am every day, while the first ride is 7:00-8:00; if there is a share between two schools, then 30 minutes are reserved for the interchange; 8:30-9:30 as the second ride. Drivers set off again by 3:00-5:30 pm, while the first one is 3:00 to 4:00 pm, and the second one is 4:30-5:30 pm.

Graph 1 School Bus Share

3.2 Efficiently use the times on Saturday and Sunday and achieve school bus share

We are all used to the schedule of 4 weeks of weekdays in school per month, but actually for Chinese students in rural area, the studying schedule can be altered to deviations. We divide each month into 6 studying sections of five days, while students study for 3 of them and rest in home for 3 of them, while students keep studying during December. We also can save the winter break, then the combination should shift to students study for 4 of studying sections and rest for 2 of them. Each cycle of this rotating studying sessions is two months. Sharing school buses with nearby schools, one half of all required school buses is saved.

School A													
School B													
Day	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-25	26-30	31-4	5-9	10-14	15-19	20-24	25-29	
Month	First						Second						Thrid
	: On class					: Off class							

Graph 2 Exemplar Cross Studying Section Arrangement

4. Use place of education support to test calculation accordingly

Based on the actual conditions of Qingxing district, the place where we voluntarily did our supporting education, we regard that the government and local companies are collectively responsible for the cost of school bus purchase and renovation and that parents and students are responsible for transportation fee are more realistic. Calculations are below:

Governmental and Company' s fee required			
#	Cost Subject	Cost (yuan)	Note
1	Bus Cost	100,000/car	
2	Renovation and repair	5,000/car	Annual milage approx. 50,000 km (31.4km*4*1.1*360=49,700km)
3	Depreciation	16,700/car*year	Each car can afford a milage of 300,000km, which mean it can afford 6 year' s usage
Total		217.000/car*year	

Parents' fee required			
#	Cost Subject	Cost	Note
1	Gas Fee	0.7/student*time	31.4km/100km*5yuan/L*1.1=17.27yuan If new fuel is being used, even less expensive
2	Driver's Salary	1.2/student*time	Assuming average monthly salary for drivers as 3000yuan/month, each driver works 30 days/month, serves 3000 students, 1.2 drivers work for each bus →average 3000*1.2/3000=1.2
3	Student Life Insurance	0.1/student*time	
Total		2/student*time	4/student*day, 20/student*week

Thus, since with all resources being fully utilized, this district requires 400 school buses in total($50000 \times 0.80 / 25 = 400$), the annual purchase and renovation cost is 8,660,000 yuan($4,000,000 \times 2.17 = 8,680,000$, approx.\$1.37million). We field interviewed several local enterprises, which all express willingness to be engaged or even responsible for full fee of advertisements at a gain of the full control of school bus advertisement.

Considering from the perspective of curtailing extraneousness, such as if drivers are at the same time being a coach of PE or an art teacher, then the salary can be included into his regular salary, then the average cost for each student for each ride can be even lowered to 1 yuan, for each day only 2 yuan. We interviewed more than 50 parents and all of them express their inclination to purchase such small fee per day. Also, we interviewed the surrounding three school other than the school that we were teaching; results showed that more than 50% of them are deft drivers, while 60% of them are willing to be a part time driver.

5. Further Discuss

In this era of Industry 4.0 and Internet+, using big data to provide safe, convenient, and comfortable school bus service is worth looking forward. There is a long way of transferring the practical experience to the actual benefits of Chinese rural elementary and middle school students to go. A large amount of internet companies have shifted their viewpoint from "hitchhiking", "express car", "special order car" to school buses. As an example, in April 1st, 2015, famous brand "Number One Special Car" announced that they were incubating a new product of name as "Number One School Bus"; 100 of them are ready to test its practicality in Beijing, and the major serving subjects are elementary students. All buses are imported from the United States and are able to hold up to 39 students per bus; windows are bulletproof glasses, and the drivers' driving experience are all over 5 years. There is also a female crew professionally trained against potential criminal for each school bus. Besides, this company also cooperates with American enterprises such as Disney, Marvel, etc. to introduce thematic features on school buses. Compared to such advanced services, we eagerly anticipate more sight of those who are concerned of the Chinese rural kids and collaborate out a more high-efficiency, convenient, applicable school bus running system, enabling those students to enjoy the existence of school buses, to learn with steadiness, and to grow up healthy physically and mentally.

Reference:

- i. Qiang, Wang. *Mei Guo Nong Cun Jiao Yu Fa Zhan Shi. Yin Chuan: Ning Xia Ren Min Chu Ban She, 2009. Web.*
- ii. Zhao, Yanjun. "Layout Adjustment of the Rural Schools: Experience and Enlightenment of America." *Layout Adjustment of the Rural Schools: Experience and Enlightenment of America. N.p., Apr. 2005. Web. 13 Mar. 2016. <http://en.cnki.com.cn/Article_en/CJFDTOTAL-SHGJ200821019.htm>.*

- iii. Kieran Killeen, and John Sipple. *School Consolidation and Transportation Policy: An Empirical and Institutional Analysis* (n.d.): n. pag. Web. 15 Nov. 2009. 13 Mar. 2016. <<http://www.ruralchallenge.org/publications.html>>.
- iv. An, Xiaomin, and Zhihui Wu. "The School Bus System in American Primary and Secondary Schools and Its Inspiration for China." *美国中小学校车制度及其对我国的启示 The School Bus System in American Primary and Secondary Schools and Its Inspiration for China*. Institute of Rural Education, n.d. Web. 13 Mar. 2016. <<http://mall.cnki.net/magazine/Article/WGJY201104012.htm>>.
- v. Yang, Zhongfeng. "公平语境中的校车资源配置." -- 《浙江工业大学》2012 年硕士论文. N.p., n.d. Web. 13 Mar. 2016. <<http://cdmd.cnki.com.cn/Article/CDMD-10337-1013146761.htm>>.
- vi. Yuan, Hao, and Qiao Jin. "发达国家校车运营管理模式及对上海的启示_论文_百度文库." *发达国家校车运营管理模式及对上海的启示_论文_百度文库*. N.p., n.d. Web. 13 Mar. 2016. <<http://wenku.baidu.com/view/4e2cfe3187c24028915fc3b1.html>>.